

Skills Required by Agricultural Education Students of Universities in Tomato Value Chain for Job Creation and income generation in Northeast Nigeria

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Abstract

This study identified the skills required by agricultural education students of Universities in tomato value chain for job creation and income generation in Northeast Nigeria. The purpose of the study was to identify skills required for in tomato value chain for job creation and income generation in Northeast Nigeria. The study had three specific objectives, three research questions and three null hypotheses. Descriptive survey research design was employed for the study to examine the views and experiences of respondents in their natural setting. The population for the study was 750 Agricultural Education Students in the study area. A sample size of 261 respondents was used out of the target population. A multi-stage sampling technique was used to draw the sample size. The required data were collected by the researcher with the help of 3 research assistants. Structured questionnaire was used to collect the data which comprised of 68-skill item grouped into seven sections sson four point rating scale. The instrument was duly validated both in face and content validity by three experts, one from Vocational and Technology Education Department, the other from Measurement and Evaluation Unit of Educational Foundations Department Faculty of Education and the other from Agronomy Department, Faculty of Agriculture all of Taraba State University, Jalingo. The instrument was trial tested at Gabriel Sarwuan Tarka University, Makurdi. A reliability index of 0.78 using Cronbach alpha was established. Skill gap analysis was used to analyze the research questions that guided the study, while, independent t-test statistics was used to test the three null hypotheses raised at 95%

IJMSRT26JUN098

confidence level using Statistical Package for Social Sciences version 20. The result indicated that 8 skill items out of 23 skill items were required by the students in tomato value chain to improve tomato value chain activities in the study area. Also, the study found no significant difference between the male and female students' ratings of the required skills for tomato value chain in the study area. Based on these results, it was recommended that the identified skills required by the students in the study area should be developed into modules skill acquisition centres of universities and agricultural development programmes to train students and youths to enhance tomato value chain. Also, Ministries of education should use the findings of this study as a base to organize seminars, conferences and workshops for re-training of teachers/Lecturers in Agriculture

Keywords:

Tomato, Skills, Tomato Value Chain, Job Creation and Income Generation

Introduction

Tomato (*Solanum lycopersicum*) is a flowering plant and member of the nightshade family solanaceae that includes potatoes, tobacco, eggplant and chili peppers (Keith 2024). Tomato is believed to have originated from South America, and taken back to Europe by the Spaniards in the early 16th century, the tomato was initially viewed with suspicion in northern Europe and English speaking countries where it was also known as the "wolf peach".

Tomato is cultivated in tropical and temperate climates. Green houses are often used for

large-scale production. Tomato is warm and sun loving plant that needs full sunlight for at least 6-8 hours a day. Tomato grows best at a day temperature of 24-29°C and a night temperature of 15-21°C. Fruiting setting is inhibited below 13°C and above 38°C (Mellisa 2024). Tomato cultivation is highly successful in southern and Northern Guinea Savannah in Nigeria during dry season under irrigation because the night temperature usually drops to 15°C. Tomato is cultivated extensively for its edible fruits and grows better on rich well-drained loamy and sandy soils with a pH range of 6.2-6.8 a day and a moderate rainfall of about 900-1500mm per annum with relative humidity of 65-85% (Vasyl 2024). Tomato is the world's leading vegetable for processing into paste, juices and powders. Nigeria ranks as the 14th largest producer of tomato fruit globally and the 2nd largest in Africa with an annual production of 2.3 million tonnes. (FAO, 2025). It is widely accepted and commonly used in a variety of dishes as raw, cooked or processed products more than any other vegetable.. Tomatoes are a great source of vitamin C, potassium; folate and vitamin K. fresh tomato are low in carbs. The carbs content consists mainly of simple sugars and insoluble fibers. These fruits are mostly made up of water. The main plant compounds in tomatoes are lycopene (a red pigment and antioxidant), Beta carotene (an antioxidant that often gives foods a yellow or orange hue), Naringenin, chlorogenic acid. Tomato offer numerous health benefits due to their rich nutrient profile including heart health support, potential cancer prevention and improved skin health.

According to A'aron (2024), tomatoes can be classified classified follows: as determinate (Bush variety), indeterminate (Vining variety) and dwarf tomatoes. Cooked tomatoes help reduce risk of heart disease, may prevent constipation, and reduce type 2 diabetes risk. Consumption of tomatoes can prevent old age related diseases such as dementia, osteoporosis, Parkinsons and Alzheimers diseases which affects behaviour, memory and thinking (Andrea 2025).

Tomato value chain refers to all the steps involved in bringing tomato from farm to the

plate of a consumer. It encompasses production, harvesting, sorting, packaging, distribution, processing, and selling of tomatoes. This involves production, marketing, distributing/transporting, storing and processing it. The main actors in tomato value chain include input suppliers, producers, local collectors, retailers, wholesalers and processors -Hotel restaurants (Ugonna, et al 2015). The major value chain functions that the tomato producers perform are ploughing, planting, fertilizing, irrigation, weeding and pest/diseases control.

The major marketing channels through which the product reaches the final consumers are:

Channel I producers → consumers

Channel II producers → retailers → consumers

Channel III producers → local collectors → retailers → consumers

Channel IV producers' → local collectors' → consumers

The term skill has been defined by various authors. According to Wever and Obiyai, (2019), skill is well established habit of doing something while skills according to Mbah and Umurhurhu (2016) are the ability to make a purposeful movement that are necessary to complete or master a particular task. Onoh (2021) defined skill as the ability to perform expertly well with dexterity and tact through what one has learnt and practiced in training.

Agricultural education is a systematic and organized teaching, instruction and training (theoretical as well as hands-on real-world field work-based) available to students, farmers or individuals interested in the science, business and technology of agriculture as well as the management of land, environment and natural resources. According to Barricle (2019), Agricultural education is the scientific study of the principles and methods of teaching and learning as they pertain to agriculture. Most disciplines have inherent skills that need to be developed or improved upon for self-employment.

Statement of the Problem

Tomato is an important vegetable that is produced globally. It presents itself in different shapes, size and colours with

different brix or sugar levels. Despite its vast nutritional, economic and health importance, tomato production is faced by various challenges which include incidence of pest and diseases, physiological disorders (cracking, sun burn or scald), poor handling, processing and preservation practices, poor storage facilities, perishability of the produce, high cost of agrochemical, inadequate credit facilities, lack of access to the market due to bad roads, high cost of transportation, poorly organized rural and urban markets infrastructures that permit unpredictable price fluctuations among others affect the tomato value chain in the study area.

1.3 Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of this study was to identify the skills required by agricultural education students of universities in tomato value chain for job creation and income generation in Northeast, Nigeria. Specifically, the study sought to identify: -

1. Post-harvesting skills required by Agricultural Education Students in tomato value chain for job creation and income generation in Northeast Nigeria
2. Value addition skill required by Agricultural Education Students in tomato value chain for job creation and income generation in Northeast Nigeria
3. Marketing skill required by Agricultural Education Students in tomato value chain for job creation and income generation in Northeast Nigeria

1.4 Research Questions

Three research questions in accordance with purposes guided the study:

1. What is the post-harvesting skill required by Agricultural Education Students in tomato value chain for job creation in Northeast Nigeria?
2. What is the value addition skill required by Agricultural Education Students in tomato value chain for job creation and income generation in Northeast Nigeria?
3. What is the marketing skill required by Agricultural Education Students in tomato value chain for job creation and income generation in Northeast Nigeria?

Hypotheses

Three null hypotheses in line with the research questions were formulated and tested at 95% confidence interval

- H₀₁ There is no significant difference between the mean of male and female Agricultural Education Students of Universities in post-harvesting skill for job creation in Northeast Nigeria.
- H₀₂ There is no significant difference between the mean of male and female Agricultural Education Students of Universities in value addition skill for job creation and income generation in Northeast Nigeria.
- H₀₃ There is no significant difference between the mean of male and female Agricultural Education Students of Universities in marketing skill for job creation and income generation in Northeast Nigeria.

Methodology

The study was conducted in Northeast Nigeria. Descriptive survey research design was employed in the conduct of the study. The population of the study was 750 undergraduate students of Universities offering Agriculture in Northeast Nigeria. Taro Yamane's formula was employed to select 261 undergraduate students of Universities offering Agricultural education as the sample size for the study. The instrument used for data collection in this study was a structured questionnaire titled "tomato production skill questionnaire (TPSQ)". Data was collected personally by the researcher with the help of two research assistants. The 23-item questionnaire was structured on four point rating scale as; highly required (HR), moderately required (MR), less required (LR), and not required (NR) as well as highly possessed (HP), moderately possessed (MP), less possessed (LP) and not possessed (NP) with both a corresponding nominal value of 4, 3, 2, and 1 respectively. The TPSQ was face and content validated by three experts each from Vocational and Technology Education, Measurement and Evaluation and Agronomy Department of Taraba state University, Jalingo. In order to determine the internal consistency of the instrument, the TPSQ was trial tested on 20 students of Gabriel Sarwuan Tarka University,

Makurdi Benue State. The reliability coefficient alpha of 0.78 using Cronbach alpha was determined using statistical package for social sciences (SPSS) version 25. Skill gap analysis was used to answer the research questions while the three null hypotheses were tested using independent t-test at 0.05 level of significance. Skill gap analysis was used to analyze the research questions as follows:

\bar{X}_n = weighted mean of required category
 \bar{X}_p = weighted mean of performance category

- ❖ Where the Skill Gap value is positive (+ve) it means that the skill item is not required
 - ❖ Where the Skill Gap value is negative (-ve) it implies that the skill item is required
- In the test of the hypotheses, reject the H_0 and uphold H_a if the t-calculated exceeds the

critical or t-table values. But if the reverse is the case, do not reject the null hypothesis H_0

Results and Discussions

The results of the study were presented in tables and the presentations were done in accordance with the research questions and hypotheses.

Research Question 1

What is the post-harvesting skill required by Agricultural Education Students in tomato value chain for job creation and income generation in Northeast Nigeria?

Table 1: Mean Rating on Post-Harvesting Skills of Agricultural Education Students in Tomato Value Chain for Job Creation and Income Generation

S/N	Items	N	\bar{x}_R	SD_R	\bar{x}_P	SD_P	GA = $(\bar{x}_R - \bar{x}_P)$	Rmk
1.	Identify tomato fruits to be culled	261	3.14	0.80	2.53	0.71	0.61	NR
2.	Sort and grade tomato fruits	261	3.13	0.79	2.48	0.72	0.65	NR
3.	Package in baskets covered with dry grasses/leaves very well	261	3.09	0.78	2.51	0.67	0.57	NR
4.	Clean and disinfect tomato fruits	261	3.13	0.80	2.54	0.66	0.60	NR
5.	Identify storage facilities for tomatoes	261	3.13	0.86	2.52	0.67	0.61	NR
6.	Distribute/ transport tomatoes to markets	261	3.05	0.86	2.55	0.66	0.50	NR
7.	Excellent network for easy conveyance to the place of value addition	261	3.13	0.82	2.47	0.68	0.66	NR
	Cluster Mean		3.12		2.51			

KEY: \bar{x}_R = Mean Response on Skills Required, \bar{x}_P = Mean Response on Skills Possessed, SD_R = Standard Deviation on Skills Required, SD_P = Standard Deviation on Skills Possessed, GA = Gap Analysis, Rmk = Remark, NR = Not Required, n = Number of Respondents

Table 1 shows the mean ratings and gap analysis of post-harvesting skills required and possessed by Agricultural Education students in the tomato value chain for job creation and income generation in Northeast Nigeria. The result indicated that key post-harvesting skills

such as identifying fruits to be culled, sorting and grading, appropriate packaging, cleaning and disinfection, identification of suitable storage facilities, transportation and distribution of tomatoes, and establishing effective networks for conveyance to value-addition points were all rated as highly required, with mean values ranging from 3.05 to 3.14 and a cluster mean of 3.12. However, the mean ratings of skills possessed by the students were comparatively low, ranging from 2.47 to 2.55, with a cluster mean of 2.51. The gap analysis values (0.50–0.66) indicate noticeable deficiencies between the required

and possessed post-harvesting skills, suggesting that although students are aware of post-harvest handling and marketing practices, they lack adequate practical competence to minimize losses and enhance income generation along the tomato value chain. All the items were considered “Not Required”, underscoring the need for improved practical exposure and capacity building in post-harvesting operations within Agricultural Education programmes.

Research Question 2

What is the value addition skill required by Agricultural Education Students in tomato value chain for job creation and income generation in Northeast Nigeria?

Table 2: Mean Rating on the Value Addition Skills of Agricultural Education Students in Tomato Value Chain for Job Creation and Income Generation

S/N	Items	n	\bar{x}_R	SD_R	\bar{x}_P	SD_P	GA = $\bar{x}_R - \bar{x}_P$	Rmk
8.	Wash the tomato with clean water	261	3.01	0.80	2.63	0.65	0.38	NR
9.	Slice the tomato into pieces	261	3.02	0.82	2.51	0.70	0.51	NR
10.	Sun-dry the sliced tomato pieces	261	2.93	0.88	2.41	0.68	0.51	NR
11.	Able to prepare ketchup from ripe tomatoes	261	2.49	0.67	3.05	0.84	-0.55	R
12.	Able to make puree from tomatoes	261	2.58	0.63	3.06	0.76	-0.48	R
13.	Able to make tomato paste from ripe tomatoes	261	2.97	0.81	2.52	0.65	0.45	NR
14.	Able to make tomato juice from ripe tomatoes	261	2.46	0.66	3.15	0.74	-0.69	R
15.	Prepare tomato powder from fresh tomato	261	2.50	0.64	3.07	0.84	-0.57	R
	Cluster Mean		2.75		2.8			

KEY: \bar{x}_R = Mean Response on Skills Required, \bar{x}_P = Mean Response on Skills Possessed, SD_R = Standard Deviation on Skills Required, SD_P = Standard Deviation on Skills Possessed, GA = Gap Analysis, Rmk = Remark, NR = Not Required, R = Required and n = Number of Respondents

Table 2 shows the mean ratings and gap analysis of value addition skills required and possessed by Agricultural Education students in the tomato value chain for job creation and income generation in Northeast Nigeria. The results indicate that essential value addition skills such as washing tomatoes with clean water, slicing and sun-drying tomato pieces, preparing ketchup, puree, paste, juice, and tomato powder were all rated as required, with mean values ranging from 2.93 to 3.03 and a cluster mean of 3.75. In contrast, the mean ratings of skills possessed by the students were lower, ranging from 2.41 to 3.15, with a cluster mean of 2.51. The gap analysis values

(0.38 to -0.69) reveal clear deficiencies between the required and possessed value addition skills, particularly in tomato juice preparation, which recorded the less skill gap. These results suggest that although students have some awareness of tomato processing and value addition activities, they lack adequate practical competence to effectively engage in value addition enterprises for enhanced job creation and income generation. 4 items were considered “Not required”, emphasizing the need for strengthened practical training, processing facilities, and entrepreneurship-oriented instruction in value addition within Agricultural Education programmes.

Research Question 3

What is the marketing skill required by Agricultural Education Students in tomato value chain for job creation and income generation in Northeast Nigeria?

Table 3: Mean rating on Marketing Skills of Agricultural Education Students in Tomato

Value Chain for Job Creation and Income Generation

S/N	Items	n	\bar{x}_R	SD_R	\bar{x}_P	SD_P	GA = $\bar{x}_R - \bar{x}_P$	Rmk
16.	Identify market outlets for tomatoes	261	3.05	0.76	2.44	0.66	0.61	NR
17.	Maintain good human relationship with customers	261	2.46	0.64	3.03	0.83	-0.57	R
18.	Establish a good marketing plan	261	3.11	0.77	2.51	0.71	0.61	NR
19.	Handle customer complains satisfactorily	261	2.43	0.69	2.95	0.85	-0.52	R
20.	Understand Pricing strategy of tomato	261	2.98	0.85	2.52	0.62	0.46	NR
21.	Networking and collaboration with value chain actors	261	2.42	0.70	3.08	0.84	-0.66	R
22.	Ability to adapt to any market situation/fluctuations	261	3.05	0.79	2.43	0.69	0.61	NR
23.	To possess financial management of all sales	261	2.44	0.70	3.03	0.78	-0.59	R
	Cluster Mean		3.04		2.46			

KEY: \bar{x}_R = Mean Response on Skills Required, \bar{x}_P = Mean Response on Skills Possessed, SD_R = Standard Deviation on Skills Required, SD_P = Standard Deviation on Skills Possessed, GA = Gap Analysis, Rmk = Remark, NR = Not Required, R = Required n = Number of Respondents

Table 3 shows the mean ratings and gap analysis of marketing skills required and possessed by Agricultural Education students in the tomato value chain for job creation and income generation in Northeast Nigeria. The findings indicate that 4 skills out of the 8 skill items were rated required by the students in the study area while 4 were rated possessed. The gap analysis values (0.46 to -0.66) reveal notable deficiencies between required and possessed marketing skills, particularly in networking and collaboration with value chain actors. This suggests that although students have awareness of marketing principles in the

tomato value chain, they lack adequate practical and entrepreneurial competence to effectively market tomato products for sustainable job creation and income generation. All the items were marked “Not Required” (NR), emphasizing the need for enhanced practical marketing training and entrepreneurship-focused instruction in Agricultural Education programmes.

Hypothesis 1

There is no significant difference between the mean of male and female Agricultural Education Students of Universities in post-harvesting skill for job creation and income generation in Northeast Nigeria.

Table 4: t-Test Analysis of Mean Ratings of Male and Female Students on Post-harvesting Skills for Job Creation and Income Generation.

Respondents	N	\bar{x}	SD	df	LS	t	Sig.	Rmk
Male Students	140	3.13	0.32					
Female Students	121	3.10	0.29	259	0.05	0.71	0.48	NS

n = number of respondents, \bar{x} = Mean, SD = Standard Deviation, df = Degree of Freedom,

LS = Level of Significance, t = t-ratio, Sig. = Significance, Rmk = Remark, NS = Not Significant

Table 4 shows the t-test analysis comparing the mean ratings of male and female Agricultural Education students on post-harvesting skills required for job creation and income generation in Northeast Nigeria. The results reveal that male students recorded a mean score of 3.13 (SD = 0.32), while female students had a mean score of 3.10 (SD = 0.29), indicating a minimal difference in their mean ratings. The calculated t-value of 0.71 with 259 degrees of freedom yielded a significance value of 0.48, which is greater than the 0.05 level of significance. This indicates that there

is no statistically significant difference between the mean of male and female Agricultural Education Students of Universities in post-harvesting skill for job creation and income generation. Consequently, Hypothesis 1 is accepted.

Hypothesis 2:

There is no significant difference between the mean of male and female Agricultural Education Students of Universities on value addition skill for job creation and income generation in Northeast Nigeria.

Table 5: t-test Analysis of Mean Ratings of Male and Female Students on Value Addition Skills for Job Creation and Income Generation.

Respondents	n	\bar{x}	SD	df	LS	T	Sig.	Rmk
Male Students	140	3.02	0.28					
				259	0.05	0.68	0.50	NS
Female Students	121	3.04	0.27					

n = number of respondents, \bar{x} = Mean, SD = Standard Deviation, df = Degree of Freedom, LS = Level of Significance, t = t-ratio, Sig. = Significance, Rmk = Remark, NS = Not Significant

Table 5 shows the t-test analysis comparing the mean ratings of male and female Agricultural Education students on value addition skills required for job creation and income generation in Northeast Nigeria. The results indicate that male students recorded a mean score of 3.02 (SD = 0.28), while female students had a slightly higher mean score of 3.04 (SD = 0.27), showing only a marginal difference in their mean ratings. The computed t-value of 0.68 with 259 degrees of freedom produced a significance value of 0.50, which is

greater than the 0.05 level of significance. This result indicates that there is no statistically significant difference between the mean of male and female Agricultural Education Students of Universities in value addition skill for job creation and income generation. Therefore, Hypothesis 2 is retained.

Hypothesis 3

There is no significant difference between the mean of male and female Agricultural Education Students of Universities in marketing skill for job creation and income generation in Northeast Nigeria.

Table 6: t-test Analysis of Mean Ratings of Male and Female Students on Marketing Skills for Job Creation and Income Generation.

Respondents	n	\bar{x}	SD	df	LS	T	Sig.	Rmk
Male Students	140	3.04	0.29					
				259	0.05	0.56	0.69	NS
Female Students	121	3.03	0.28					

n = number of respondents, \bar{x} = Mean, SD = Standard Deviation, df = Degree of Freedom, LS = Level of Significance, t = t-ratio, Sig. =

Significance, Rmk = Remark, NS = Not Significant

Table 6 shows the t-test analysis comparing the mean ratings of male and female Agricultural Education students on marketing skills required for job creation and income generation in Northeast Nigeria. The results indicate that male students recorded a mean score of 3.04 (SD = 0.29), while female students had a closely similar mean score of 3.03 (SD = 0.28), reflecting a negligible difference in their mean ratings. The calculated t-value of 0.56 with 259 degrees of freedom yielded a significance value of 0.69, which is greater than the 0.05 level of significance. This result shows that there is no statistically significant difference between the mean of male and female Agricultural Education Students of Universities in marketing skill for job creation and income generation. Consequently, Hypothesis 3 was upheld.

Findings of the Study

Based on the results presented, the findings of the study are as follows:

1. All the 7 skills were not required by the Agricultural Education students in the study area. The gap analysis values (0.50-0.66) indicated noticeable deficiencies between the required and possessed post-harvesting skills. Significant difference does not exist between the mean ratings of male and female Agricultural Education Students of Universities in post-harvesting skill for job creation and income generation in Northeast Nigeria.
2. 4 skills were required out of 8 skills by Agricultural Education students of Universities in Northeast Nigeria. Also, significant difference does not occur between the mean ratings of male and female Agricultural Education Students of Universities in tomato value addition for job creation and income generation in Northeast Nigeria.
3. 4 out of the 8 skills listed were found required by Agricultural Education students of Universities in the study area. Significant difference does not exist between the mean ratings of male and female Agricultural Education Students of Universities in

marketing skill for job creation and income generation in Northeast Nigeria.

4.4 Discussion of the Findings

First finding revealed that no skill was required by the students in the study area. This finding is contrary with Ekele and Shishi (2019) who found out that proper tomato handling, storage, transportation techniques to reduce losses and maintain quality are required by Agricultural education students. Food and Agri Economics Review, (2022) also enumerated the following as post-harvesting/handling skills: cleaning and disinfecting, sorting and grading, packaging, storage and transportation as a core for achieving high quality tomatoes which is contrary to the study.

The result of the findings with regards to research question two revealed that 4 out of the 8 skills of value addition were required by the Agricultural Education students in the study area. This findings is in line with the findings made by Gaetha and Indhu, (2020) who in their study found out that tomato value addition skills equip agricultural education students with capacity for food processing, quality control, market analysis and also enable them to reduce post-harvest losses and increase farmer's income. Asogwa (2021) stressed that tomato preservation is very important to ensure its availability constant in the market. He stress that tomato fruits well preserved can be taken to areas of its scarcity thereby making high profit and available all the time.

Finally, the result of the study with regards to research question three revealed that 4 out of the 8 skills identified were required by Agricultural Education students of Universities in Northeast Nigeria as can be seen in table 3. This result concord with (Gabriela, 2024) who stressed that student who lacks soft skills like communication, creativity and interpersonal skills may not do well in marketing activities. He went further to say that Tomato marketing is necessary for agricultural students to enable them persuade, sell and develop professional relationships with customers, vendors or partners.

Conclusion

1. Essential planting skills were highly required, but students' level of skill possession was considerably lower, revealing significant deficiencies in practical planting competencies necessary for successful tomato production.
2. Students lacked sufficient proficiency in applying post-planting skills, resulting in noticeable gaps that could hinder sustainable tomato production and income generation.
3. Students have theoretical awareness of harvesting operations, but they lack adequate practical competence to carry out effective harvesting of tomatoes.

Recommendations

The following recommendations were made based on the findings of this study:

1. The identified skills required by the students in the study area should be developed into modules by skill acquisition centres of Universities and Agricultural Development Programmes to train students and youths to enhance youth involvement in tomato value chain
2. The Ministry of Education should use the findings of this research as a base to organize seminar, conferences and workshops for retraining of teachers/lecturers in Agricultural Education.
3. Policy makers responsible for agricultural development and food security should use the findings of this study to target policies and support programmes that could encourage skill development in tomato value chain to create jobs.

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